

Control Parameter Estimation Encompassing Time and Frequency Domain Test Cases Using Particle Swarm Optimization

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Abstract

As the penetration of inverter-based resources (IBRs) in power grids increases, the need for accurate models becomes important to ensure reliable grid planning and operation. Electromagnetic transient (EMT) studies using detailed models can capture important system dynamics, but these models often lack availability or are computationally demanding. To address these challenges, standardized and flexible generic models have been proposed, though their calibration remains a key issue. This paper presents a parameter estimation framework designed to improve the calibration of generic IBR models, employing Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). The focus is on integrating data from both Time and Frequency Domain testing to capture the system dynamics, and use these data to calibrate key control parameters. While the framework is mainly conceptualized to utilize data collected from Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) setups, it is flexible enough to be adapted to different cases, e.g., including other model parameters, and leveraging different types of data, such as offline simulation or measurement data. The proposed framework is demonstrated through a Type-4 generic wind turbine model, estimating six proportional-integral (PI) control parameters across active power, reactive power, and RMS voltage control loops. The study explores the use of different test cases and sensitivity analysis to optimize the calibration process. Results from proof-of-concept experiments showed that Time Domain data alone could effectively calibrate these parameters, providing a close match to reference values. Due to the overlap between control bandwidths of this specific subset, Frequency Domain testing was not advantageous in this case. The findings suggest that although Frequency Domain data might offer benefits, its application is context-dependent, especially when overlapping control dynamics are present. Future work will expand the framework to integrate all key grid-following control parameters and further explore the benefits of combining Time and Frequency Domain data for parameter calibration.

1 Introduction

As the penetration of IBRs increases in power grids, the need for accurate models of IBR in planning studies becomes more critical [1, 2]. It has been demonstrated that EMT studies with detailed Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEMs) models are needed to capture important dynamics of the system, particularly under weak grid conditions [1]. On the other hand, publicly available, standardized, flexible, and openly documented generic models has been highlighted to be important tools to better understand and mitigate emerging reliability concerns related to IBRs connected to the Bulk Power System (BPS) [3, 4].

This demand stems from the fact that, although OEM frequently provide either simplified IBR models or IBR models containing a compiled version of the original controller source code to protect their property information, these models might not be available, or they may be too computationally demanding for real-time or large-scale simulations. As a result, the Western Electricity Coordinating Council (WECC) has worked

with a collaborative community of stakeholders to release the second generation of IBR generic models in 2016/17, with new modules being added in recent years [3]. It has been shown that standardized generic models can be highly relevant to specific applications, capturing close approximates of the dynamic behavior of the system, if properly calibrated [4, 5].

However, research on the validation and calibration of generic IBR models remains limited, partly due to the restricted access to proprietary information of commercial inverters, which reduces the range of previously presented methods that can be effectively applied to calibrating these models. For example, parameter calibration approaches used on synchronous generator models, which rely on Kalman-filtering algorithms, might not be extended to IBR models with a wide variety of control structures and no standardized IBR reference models. This hinders the establishment of a standard analytical state-space model of the system and, consequently, its calibration. Despite these challenges, previous studies have demonstrated that these generic models can be calibrated using data from Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) [5].

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the grid-following (GFL) control strategy, focusing on its control architecture. In Section 3, the proposed parameter estimation framework is presented in detail. Section 4 shows and discuss the results for the specific proof-of-concept use case. Finally, the main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- Development of a flexible parameter estimation framework for IBR models using PSO.
- Integration of Time and Frequency Domain data to calibrate control parameter of IBR models.
- Demonstration of the framework using a proof-of-concept use case based on a generic type-4 WTG model.

2 Grid-following Converter

Inverter control strategies are generally classified into two main categories: grid-following (GFL) and grid-forming (GFM). The GFL inverter technology is currently dominant in grid-connected applications. A GFL inverter functions as a current source, which focuses on regulating its current injection into the grid. Unlike grid-forming inverters, which actively control both voltage and frequency as slack-bus or through a power-synchronization, GFL inverters rely on the measurement of the grid's voltage angle for synchronization, assuming that the voltage waveform and frequency are provided externally by, preferably, a strong grid defined by a SCR (Short Circuit Ratio) higher than 5 [6].

As depicted in Fig. 1, the general architecture of a grid-following control scheme includes multiple control levels. The inverter-level control is responsible for managing the active and reactive power flows based on the phase-locked loop (PLL) and current controller [7]. The PLL ensures that the inverter synchronizes with the grid voltage, providing information about

the grid voltage angle θ_{gd} and frequency f_{gd} . This synchronization is crucial for aligning the output current i_o with the grid voltage at the connection terminal v_t .

The active-power and reactive-power controllers are tasked with regulating the power output P_t and Q_t , in which the references are provided by the plant-level control. In turn, the plant-level control regulates the inverter's active and reactive power based on droop controllers that respond to deviations in grid frequency f_t and voltage v_t . Droop control strategies can vary depending on the application and operational requirements. Besides the standard P/f and Q/V droop controllers, alternative control schemes such as constant power factor control, fixed active/reactive power (P/Q) control, fixed AC voltage (V_t) control, active power reference from DC capacitor's voltage (E_{DC}) or others can be employed [7].

Although the framework proposed in this work is designed to be generic and applicable to different models, to demonstrate its practical implementation a specific example of a Type-4 generic wind turbine model is used. The primary objective of this demonstration is to conduct a proof-of-concept to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed framework and its associated steps, which involved, in this case, the estimation of six PI (proportional-integral) control parameters across the active power, P_t , reactive power Q_t , and RMS voltage V_t control loops. The control structures used for this purpose are depicted in Figure 2. These control structures represent an adapted subset of the REEC_D model, which is part of the second-generation IBR generic models introduced by the WECC under the Renewable Energy Modeling Task Force (REMTF) [3].

Fig. 1: General Grid-following control scheme.

Fig. 2: Control diagrams for (a) Active Power and (b) Local Coordinated Q/V Control.

3 Parameter Estimation Framework

A similar framework was previously presented, aiming to validate and calibrate inverter models using Phasor Measurement Unit (PMU) data [5]. The authors demonstrated the application of their proposed framework using Bayesian optimization on generic GFL and GFM inverter models within the GridLAB-D simulation platform, an open-source tool designed for the dynamic simulation of three-phase distribution networks in the phasor domain. While there are some similarities between this previous framework and the methodology presented here, differences arise in terms of application and the expected data. Specifically, the framework proposed in this paper focus on integrating Time and Frequency Domain data from HIL setups and laboratory testing, such as from grid code certification test results. Regarding HIL setups, an important source of high-fidelity data for model calibration is the use of HIL-compatible models. Real-time simulator manufacturers, such as Typhoon HIL, have collaborated with OEMs to offer ready-to-deploy package solutions that include both hardware, accompanying models and documentation. These solutions are accessible to third parties, with the added assurance that the manufacturer’s IP protection is fully maintained through the HIL-compatible structure.

This approach bypasses several limitations associated with PMU data, such as the difficulty in recreating specific scenarios in the field and challenges in distinguishing actual system events from data anomalies. Consequently, there is no need for modules like event detection, data preprocessing, or sanity checks, which are essential in frameworks relying on field data. This freedom allows for the selection of more suitable test cases tailored to specific calibration needs. The proposed framework is implemented using Particle Swarm Optimization and the Typhoon HIL software suite and its automated test environment, which allows for more controlled and replicable testing conditions.

The framework, depicted in Fig. 3, is structured around three key phases: the Conceptual Phase, the Optimization Strategy Tuning Phase, and the Estimation and Assessment Phase. While the framework is adaptable to various models, the specific results of the presented steps may vary depending on the practical case being analyzed. This variability highlights why the Conceptual Phase and the Optimization Strategy Tuning Phase are inherently iterative processes within the framework. For instance, insights gained during the Optimization Strategy Tuning Phase may indicate the need to revisit and adjust what was defined in the Conceptual Phase.

An essential aspect of these iterations involves the design of test cases, which are directly linked to the selection of key parameters for estimation. The IBRs, driven by their controls, may exhibit highly non-linear behavior when conditions such as saturation or a sudden change in control mode are met. Therefore, it is important to select the operational points far from potential saturation and conditions when conducting the analysis and, thus, apply the optimization method for the parameter estimation. Ensuring that the calibrated model is

Fig. 3: Proposed Parameter Estimation Framework

both relevant and representative of the specific cases to be studied is fundamental to achieving valid and applicable results. This understanding is important for choosing suitable control parameters and designing test cases that provide effective references for calibration. Additionally, this process is complemented by parameter sensitivity analysis, which explores how changes in one or a set of parameters can affect the system’s behavior under the designed test cases. The outcomes of this particular application will be discussed later in the paper.

3.1 Time Domain Test Cases

When choosing test cases, the goal is to select those where the dynamic behavior is affected by the key parameters being calibrated. If the resulting behavior of a perturbation, or a segment of this behavior, are affected only by a subset of the parameters to be calibrated, the calibration process can be simplified by reducing the problem dimension, concentrating on those specific parameters. In the specific example presented in this paper, the focus involves estimating six PI control parameters across the active power, reactive power, and RMS voltage control loops of a generic GFL control model. The selected test cases comprise a sequence of steps applied to the active power and RMS voltage references.

Fig. 4 illustrates the set of steps applied to the active power and RMS voltage references. Three different experiments are presented. In 4a two test cases are shown, focusing on shorter, more concentrated perturbations, in which the steps changes are applied exclusively to the active power reference, P_t^* , or to the voltage reference V_t^* . By limiting the scope of the test to a particular subset of the control, it allows for better grouping of parameters and reducing the complexity of the parameter space that needs to be tuned.

Fig. 4: Time-Domain Test Cases with step changes applied to the active power or RMS voltage references: (a) Experiments, focusing on shorter, more concentrated perturbations with steps changes applied exclusively to the active power reference, P_t^* , or to the voltage reference V_t^* . (b) Experiment comprising a sequence of reference step changes applied to the active power reference, P_t^* , and to the voltage reference V_t^* .

On the other hand, in 4b the experiment involves a sequence of step changes in both P_t^* and V_t^* . At the start of the calibration process, when parameter estimates may be significantly inaccurate, using a broader test case that captures the system's dynamics across a wide range of operating points can be advantageous. This approach helps establish an initial estimate for a larger set of parameters, providing a better starting point for subsequent optimization. By varying the step changes – sometimes adjusting only the active power reference, sometimes only the RMS voltage reference, and in some cases, altering both simultaneously – the goal is to generalize the scenario and avoid restricting the calibration to a specific operational point.

The process involves applying a step change and then letting the signal settle before applying the subsequent step, ensuring that each dynamic response is fully observed before proceeding. However, the total calibration process time depends on the duration of the experiments. Since each particle of the swarm runs this full experiment once per iteration, the total calibration time can increase significantly. To address this, one could optimize the process by selecting fewer but still relevant perturbations, thereby reducing the overall experiment time while maintaining calibration accuracy.

3.2 Frequency Domain Test Cases

The utilization of frequency domain data provides an alternative way for assessing the impact of controller parameters on a model's dynamic response. By employing frequency response analysis to examine the relationship between input and output, this approach facilitates extracting impedance characteristics, defined as the ratio between the injected current/voltage and measured voltage/current, across a wide range of frequencies at different operational points. This is particularly advantageous when working with IBR models, often provided as EMT black-boxed models, thanks to the possibility of extracting meaningful information via injection and measurement of current and voltage at the terminals. This enables a better understanding of system behavior without requiring detailed internal knowledge of the model structure.

There are various frequency scanning methods available for obtaining the harmonic impedance of IBRs [8–10]. Among these, the p-scan method was chosen for this experiment due to its ease of implementation and widespread adoption by transmission system operators (TSOs). The p-scan method is a single-input single-output (SISO) approach in the sense that separate injections should be applied for each sequence. In this experiment, only the positive sequence component (p-scan) is applied because, in this specific WTG model, the control system is designed to respond solely to positive sequence quantities. Additionally, the fact that the WTG transformer is connected in Delta on the high-voltage side, the zero-sequence components are not relevant.

The injection of an excitation signal can be performed using either a parallel current signal or a voltage signal in series to the analyzed device. For the system under consideration, a voltage injection method has been chosen. This approach involves injecting a voltage signal with a relatively small amplitude, e.g. 10% of the voltage source amplitude, in series with the source power system, with measurements taken at the grid side turbine's converter terminals to assess the system's response, as illustrated in Fig. 5. To ensure the accuracy of the impedance measurements, the WTG model should be disconnected from the interconnected network and connected to an ideal voltage source [10]. This is necessary because any other dynamic component, unbalance in the network or the presence of other power electronic components can generate non-characteristic harmonics and inter-harmonics, which could compromise the accuracy of the impedance measurements. In addition, the Impedance analysis method has to be based on the open-loop measurement of the IBR and grid's equivalent impedance. This is because Bode and Nyquist's stability criteria evaluate the open-loop gain to evaluate the closed-loop stability.

Fig. 5: Small-signal harmonic voltage injection scheme.

In the context of non-linear system as in IBRs, the principle of superposition does not hold true. However, they can be considered linear for small changes around an operating point and far from a potential operation that can trigger controllers' saturation [11]. The choice of injected signal waveform is important in this process. A sinusoidal excitation, or single-tone injection, provides the small-signal harmonic impedance at a specific frequency. However, if the amplitude of the sinewaves is not correctly evaluated, the injection may move the system to another undesired operational point if the amplitude is too high or not be distinguishable from noise measurement if it is too small; moreover, this method is time-consuming when scanning the entire frequency range of interest. An alternative approach is multi-tone injection, which involves simultaneously injecting a set of harmonics. This method yields the harmonic impedance for small changes around an operating point across the corresponding frequency range, with a single multi-tone injection. However, careful consideration must be given to the magnitude and phase separation of these harmonics to maintain the small-signal requirement. For example, the injected signal for phase a can be determined as follows:

$$e_{a,inj}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^N A_k \sin(2\pi f_k t + \phi_{a,k}), \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of frequency components for the specified frequency range, A_k is the amplitude of the k th frequency component, f_k is the k th frequency, and $\phi_{a,k}$ is the phase of the k th frequency component for phase A. To mitigate constructive interference, harmonics of equal magnitude with a quadratic phase shift are employed for each frequency component [11], and the frequency range is kept within octaves.

By injecting a small-signal voltage perturbation into the system and measuring the resulting current response, the impedance across different frequencies can be estimated using Fourier analysis [10]. Specifically, the harmonic impedance for phase A of the inverter-based resource (IBR) within the specified frequency range is calculated as:

$$Z_{\text{measured}}(f) = \frac{\mathcal{F}[V_{a,\text{meas}}(t)]}{\mathcal{F}[I_{a,\text{meas}}(t)]}, \quad (2)$$

where $V_{a,\text{meas}}(t)$ and $I_{a,\text{meas}}(t)$ are the time-domain measured voltage and current at the IBR's terminal, respectively, as illustrated in Fig. 5. The operator \mathcal{F} denotes the Fourier transform, which converts the time-domain signals into their frequency-domain representations.

3.3 Cost Function

In the context of optimization, a cost function is a mathematical formula that maps one or more variables to a real number representing the cost or loss, which is defined by the error between estimated and reference outputs. When designing a cost function, several key factors must be considered to ensure meaningful results. One such factor is data normalization, which is crucial when handling diverse input types. In this WTG generic model calibration example case, the

IBR's harmonic impedance magnitude and phase are used for frequency-domain and currents in q and d frames and average RMS voltage are used when calculating the cost for time-domain. These time-domain quantities were chosen because they are fundamental to power calculation and can be used to derive other important quantities. By per-unitizing their values, normalization ensures that all inputs contribute equally, preventing any single feature from disproportionately influencing the cost function.

The cost function is derived using the Euclidean distance between predicted and actual values. Euclidean distance is both straightforward to compute and intuitive to interpret. It represents the "straight-line" distance between two points, providing a direct measure of the total error by computing the square root of the sum of squared differences between the estimated and reference values. Mathematically, it can be expressed as:

$$\text{Cost} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (3)$$

where y_i denotes the reference value, \hat{y}_i is the estimated value, and N is the total number of data points. However, when the number of data points between the estimated and reference datasets is different, using Euclidean distance may be impractical. In such cases, the area under the curve (AUC) serves as a possible alternative, particularly after applying preprocessing steps, e.g., removing offsets in the curve [5]. The trapezoidal rule is frequently employed to calculate the AUC due to its simplicity and accuracy in numerical integration. It approximates the area by summing the areas of trapezoids formed under the curve.

Simulated environments allow for flexibility in generating reference data, enabling the secure generation of events and the collection of corresponding data without being constrained by historical measurements, where both the occurrence of past events and the quality of data obtained from it limit the reference data. In fact, poor data quality, such as low sampling rates or noisy measurements, can impact the performance of model calibration. Additionally, there are often data protection and privacy concerns when using sensitive measurements from real systems, which can restrict access to suitable data. Simulation setups, however, bypass these issues, providing high flexibility over the test cases and sampling rates.

3.4 Parameter Sensitivity Analysis

It is important to systematically assess how variations in control parameters influence the inverter's performance under the chosen test cases. Thus, in this step, the goal is to ensure that the parameters to be calibrated are sensitive enough to the chosen test cases so that the iterative parameter estimation routine can effectively calibrate them. First, the boundaries for each control parameter has to be defined. The boundaries limit the search scope during the iterative parameter estimation routine and they are also helpful in the sensitivity analysis phase.

While the second-generation generic model introduced by WECC may provide standard values and corresponding limits,

engineering expertise and system-specific knowledge can often guide the estimation of reasonable parameter boundaries. It is important to ensure that the test cases and parameter boundaries reflect real-world operating conditions and encompass the inverter's operational envelope. If some parameters exhibit low sensitivity, consider adding or modifying test cases to better capture the inverter dynamics influenced by those parameters.

Sensitivity analysis should be conducted for all test cases, both in the time domain and frequency domain. When a specific set of parameters is fixed and the analysis is performed on one variable while holding the others constant, the results are specific to that particular configuration and operational point. Different results can be expected when a different set of fixed parameters or operational point is used.

In Fig. 6, the sensitivities of the PI controllers measured for phase A are shown. The purpose of this experiment is to analyze how variations in the parameters of the outer-loop controller, K_p and K_i , impact the harmonic impedance of the inverter on that specific system configuration and operational point. To explore the parameter space, a factorial design approach is employed. Predefined low, medium, and high values are selected for each parameter, within their respective boundaries. This results in nine possible combinations for each PI controller, as both K_p and K_i are varied across three values each.

By holding the parameters of the other controllers constant, the effect of one controller's parameters on the harmonic impedance can be assessed for that specific system configuration and operational point. In addition, it is known from the structure of IBR control that the cascade controller must not have overlapping bandwidth; this aspect may simplify the calibration procedure in the frequency domain since each couple K_p and K_i have an effect just in a specific frequency range. This approach allows us to directly attribute any observed changes in impedance to variations in the parameters of the

controller under investigation. The solid curve represents the mean harmonic impedance value obtained from all tested cases for each PI controller. Each curve is accompanied by a shaded region that indicates ± 1 standard deviation from the mean. The wider this envelope, the greater the standard deviation, indicating more variability in the harmonic impedance.

Notably, the sensitivity varies across frequencies, with more pronounced effects in the fundamental frequency region since the calibration is done just on outer loop controllers, as shown by the increased magnitude and phase deviations. This observation has important implications for optimization routines, as focusing on this sensitive frequency range can reduce computational time by avoiding unnecessary scans over less sensitive regions. Additionally, this analysis may facilitate better grouping of parameters for the optimization process, enabling the isolation of the effects of one set of parameters over another.

To conduct a sensitivity analysis using time-domain data, a structured workflow can be applied. This workflow includes parameter variation, time-domain simulation, data extraction, and sensitivity analysis. Specifically, a selected parameter is varied within a specified range to observe its effect on the inverter's dynamic response. Key performance metrics, such as overshoot, settling time, and rate of change, are extracted from the simulation results to quantify the system's performance. These metrics are then analyzed to evaluate the sensitivity of the inverter's response to changes in the investigated parameter. Visualization techniques, such as plotting overshoot or settling time against the parameter, can further aid in interpreting the sensitivity for the chosen test cases.

3.5 PSO and Hyperparameter Selection

PSO is a population-based optimization algorithm developed by Kennedy and Eberhart [12, 13]. The method simulates how individual agents, called particles, move within a solution space to converge towards an optimal solution. The goal of the swarm is to find the most optimal solution. In the context of parameter calibration, the swarm of particles explores a D -dimensional solution space, where D corresponds to the number of parameters to be calibrated. Each particle i is represented by a position vector $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{iD})$, where x_{ij} represents the value of the j -th parameter for particle i . The velocity of each particle i is denoted by $\mathbf{v}_i = (v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{iD})$, and it determines how the particle's position is updated over iterations.

Each particle's position in the search space is updated according to the equation:

$$\mathbf{x}_i(t+1) = \mathbf{x}_i(t) + \mathbf{v}_i(t+1) \quad (4)$$

The velocity update equation is given by:

$$\mathbf{v}_i(t+1) = w\mathbf{v}_i(t) + c_1r_1[\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{x}_i(t)] + c_2r_2[\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{x}_i(t)] \quad (5)$$

where w is the inertia weight that balances the particle's momentum and exploration; c_1 is the cognitive learning rate, representing the importance of the particle's personal best position; c_2 is the social learning rate, representing the importance

Fig. 6: Sensitivity analysis of the harmonic impedance response (magnitude and phase) for the active power (P) PI controller, terminal RMS voltage (Vrms) PI controller, and reactive power (Q) controller for the specific generic wind turbine model. The solid lines represent the mean values, while the shaded regions indicate ± 1 standard deviation from the mean.

of the swarm's best position (global best); r_1 and r_2 are random values between 0 and 1; p_i is the particle's personal best position; and g is the global best position found by the swarm.

The behavior and performance of PSO are highly influenced by the three key hyperparameters: cognitive learning rate (c_1), social learning rate (c_2), and inertia weight (w). These hyperparameters govern how much influence the particle's personal experience and swarm experience have on its position updates.

Cognitive Learning Rate (c_1): The cognitive learning rate c_1 controls how much a particle relies on its own personal best experience. Higher c_1 values encourage exploration based on individual experiences, increasing the chance of discovering the global optimum but slowing down convergence. Conversely, lower c_1 values promote faster convergence but may lead to getting stuck in local optima.

Social Learning Rate (c_2): The social learning rate c_2 determines how much a particle is influenced by the best position found by the swarm (global best). A higher c_2 value enhances exploitation by promoting convergence towards the best-found solution, but may reduce the chances of discovering other promising regions. Lower c_2 values favor exploration, enabling the particles to investigate broader areas of the search space, delaying convergence but potentially finding better solutions.

Inertia Weight (w): The inertia weight w controls the particle's momentum by balancing exploitation (using the particle's past velocity) and exploration (gathering new information). Higher w values allow particles to explore further in their current direction, which could increase the likelihood of missing close optima. Lower w values encourage the particles to focus more on recent information, improving convergence but limiting exploration.

3.6 Iterative Parameter Estimation Routine

Fig. 7 illustrates potential steps involved in the iterative parameter estimation routine. In this example, a two-layer process is proposed, with one layer utilizing frequency domain data and the other time domain data. However, these steps, including the layer numbers, the perturbations and the data types, should be defined by the specific considered use-case. In this process, a subset of parameters is calibrated while others remain fixed.

In [5], the authors proposed a methodology utilizing Bayesian optimization, where parameter grouping was found to accelerate the calibration process, with performance depending on how the parameters are grouped and their predefined bounds. Their approach involved iterating within each parameter group until a tolerance threshold was achieved or a certain number of iterations was reached. Similarly, in the framework proposed here, the parameter grouping yielded better results by reducing the parameter search space. However, unlike their work, PSO is employed, and the hyperparameter vector H_i is selected such that after K iterations, all particles P in the swarm converge to the vicinity of an optimum solution.

Fig. 7: Iterative parameter calibration routine using PSO algorithm. Two layers of calibration are proposed, one with frequency domain data and other with time domain data.

It is noteworthy that in Fig. 6 the sensitivity analysis of the three outer loops that act on similar bandwidth, as a consequence, it is difficult to calibrate singularly one controller via the analysis of injections where all the controllers are simultaneously active. The final effect is that it is not trivial to distinguish if the specific scanned impedance is influenced more by the outer voltage controller or the active power one. This results in an estimation of controller parameters that may not necessarily represent the actual ones due to their influence in the same frequency range. To address this aspect, it may be possible to act on different layers; the first might be not using a cascade controller for the voltage/reactive power at the same bandwidth. Thus, separate controllers should be used or act on different frequency ranges. For what concerns the active power controller, if it acts on the same frequency range as the voltage/reactive power ones, it may be possible to make one of the controllers inert during the injection; therefore, repeat the injection and the calibration routine twice. Another option is to have a mix of methods, such as using the frequency domain for calibration with the certainty of clear frequency separation of the controllers and using the time domain method to calibrate the controllers with an overlapping effect in the frequency domain.

4 Results and Discussions

In this section the performance of the calibration framework is observed in a specific proof-of-concept scenario, where a type-4 WTG generic model is used as described in Section 2, where the outer loop control was calibrated. The calibration

routine involved an initial run of the optimization algorithm with 10 iterations and 100 particles using time domain data to calibrate all six PI parameters simultaneously, establishing an initial estimate for the parameters. The perturbation consisted of a sequence of reference step changes applied to the active power reference, P_t^* , and to the voltage reference, V_t^* . The results are shown on Table 1.

Three subsequent calibration runs were conducted using 20 particles and 10 iterations each. Each run used the output parameters from the previous run as its starting point. The final three runs targeted individual controllers, calibrating a single PI controller per run while keeping the others fixed. Time domain data were also used in each case, but focusing on shorter, more concentrated perturbations with steps changes applied exclusively to the active power reference, P_t^* , or to the voltage reference V_t^* .

Since the outer loop controls have overlapping bandwidths as observed by the sensitivity analysis, frequency domain data did not offer much advantage in this case. As a result, only time domain data was used for calibration. If the parameter scope were broader, for example by including inner loop controls, the harmonic impedance response would likely show clearer frequency separation between these controllers. In such cases, frequency domain data could be advantageous for parameter calibration, as it would allow parameters to be grouped based on their frequency range, guided by a parameter sensitivity analysis.

Table 2 shows the reference parameters, calibrated and uncalibrated parameter values that the models were initialized with. Note that a very close match is obtained for all parameters in this proof-of-concept case using time domain data. Figure 8 shows a comparison of the simulation signals with the reference for active and reactive power (in p.u.) obtained before and after the calibration process. Similarly, Figure 9 presents the results for the same power step change, from 0.5 to 1 p.u., but this time the signals represent the currents I_d and I_q , compared

Run	K_{p1}	K_{i1}	K_{p2}	K_{i2}	K_{p3}	K_{i3}
1	0.55	46.50	0.61	9.59	0.513	51.525
2	0.33	40.58	0.61	9.59	0.513	51.525
3	0.33	40.58	0.71	10.03	0.513	51.525
4	0.33	40.58	0.71	10.03	0.99	52.68

Table 1: Obtained calibration results after each run of the calibration routine. In the first run, all six parameters were calibrated simultaneously. In subsequent runs, the parameters were fixed, and only one PI controller was calibrated per run.

Group	Parameter	Reference	Calibrated	Uncalibrated
1	k_{p1}	0.25	0.33	0.5
	k_{i1}	40	40.58	30
2	k_{p2}	0.75	0.71	0.5
	k_{i2}	10	10.03	20
3	k_{p3}	1	0.99	0.6
	k_{i3}	50	52.68	70

Table 2: Calibrated parameters for the proof-of-concept type-4 WTG generic model.

Fig. 8: Simulation results obtained for the active and reactive power in p.u. before and after parameter calibration when an active power step is applied. The reference signal is shown as the baseline for comparison.

Fig. 9: Simulation results obtained for dq-frame currents I_d and I_q in p.u. before and after parameter calibration when an active power step is applied. The reference signal is shown as the baseline for comparison.

to the reference. In both cases, it is evident that the blue dotted line, representing the uncalibrated parameter set, deviates more significantly from the reference signal.

5 Conclusion

This study presents a parameter estimation framework using Particle Swarm Optimization, focusing on improving calibration of generic IBR models. The proof-of-concept demonstrated that time domain data alone sufficed for effective calibration, closely matching reference values, as overlapping

control bandwidths restricted the use of frequency domain data. The findings suggest that while frequency domain data might offer distinct benefits, particularly when a broader parameter set is considered, its use is context-dependent. This highlights the value of thorough sensitivity analysis in choosing the appropriate data, disturbances to be applied and calibration routine.

Moving forward, the framework will be extended to a broader scope by incorporating all key grid-following and grid-forming control parameters. This expansion aims to better demonstrate the complementary benefits of using frequency domain data alongside time domain data for parameter calibration. Data collection for calibration will continue to leverage HIL setups, as the framework is mainly designed with this context in mind. Further studies will demonstrate the application of the framework using HIL setups as the main source of high-fidelity reference data for IBR generic model parameter calibration.

Legal Disclaimer

Figures and values presented in this paper should not be used to judge the performance of Typhoon HIL technology or any company as they are solely presented for demonstration purpose. Any opinions or analysis contained in this paper are the opinions of the authors.

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